

THE LEVEL OF EFFICIENCY OF THE SYSTEM FOR PREPARING STUDENTS FOR THE PROCESS OF HEALTHY SPORTS

Arabboyev Hurshid

Tashkent University of Information Technologies
Independent researcher of the Fergana branch
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Abstract: In this article, one of the main tasks of future pedagogues in modern society today is high professional competence and intellectual potential, loyalty, ideological conviction, and love for their profession. This distinguishes educators from other professions. Many programs on improving the quality and efficiency of education, forming their practical skills in subjects, and opinions on the priority tasks were expressed.

Key words and phrases: future pedagogues, new development, modern outlook, scientific-theoretical views, continuous education, individual qualities, well-rounded person, educational standards, civil society, scientific-methodology.

INTRODUCTION

Today, in the new development strategy of our country, many organizational and legal reforms are being carried out aimed at forming the process of mass sports rehabilitation in society, forming a healthy lifestyle culture in people, and increasing their indicators of healthy living. In the period of 2019-2023, in accordance with the concept of development of physical education and mass sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan, a system of training and selection of innovative thinking personnel will be created. , conducting seminars for managers, sports medical staff and psychologists, organizing experience gaining in leading world sports centers in the fields of Sport Management, Sport Leadership, Sport Administration will be done." This is also based on improving the possibilities of the pedagogical process aimed at training a healthy generation and improving the health of the nation through the improvement of the mass sports health system in our society.

Three-stage sports competitions, consisting of "Sprouts of Hope", "Barkamol Avlod", and "Universiade" are important in the development of mass sports rehabilitation in our country. After all, the implementation of the integrated system, which includes the sports games "Umid nihollari", "Barkamol Avlod", "Universiade", is of great importance in the step-by-step preparation of the youth of our country for the process of mass sports rehabilitation. The first stage of this system, "Umid Nihollar", is a small Olympiad that tests the place of physical education and sports in the activities of students, guiding them to the mass sports rehabilitation process. The criteria and conditions of the "Sprout of Hope" program, which is planned to be held gradually among students of general secondary educational institutions in our country, has become a standard that determines and prepares students for physical fitness indicators. In the pedagogical process, it is aimed to make students healthy and learn the basics of physical education to train them in sports regularly.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Stratification means taking into account the individual characteristics of students, dividing them into groups based on some of their characteristics for education. Also,

stratification is a form of creating an educational process in which the teacher and students have and works on the basis of the educational content determined according to the qualities that are important for the educational process.

The success of differentiated education depends to a large extent on how well it is related to individualized education. In this, step-by-step plans and curricula are implemented in the educational process. Separate individual training sessions will be organized for gifted students. The topics of such training sessions should be reflected in the training programs. Gifted education can have a positive impact on the development of the abilities of all classmates.

In addition to the formation of skills and competencies in physical education, the multifaceted approach is also a way to activate students. Therefore, it should be used regularly, sufficient, perfect and concise in order to fulfill its task, that is, to strengthen the health of students, to remain a factor of action that increases the level of physical fitness. The growth and development of the students' body, the pace and direction of their individual physical development are encouraged only if they are selected correctly. Such children require more attention to the students when choosing exercises in relation to others, and when regulating them. Thus, educational technology is a method of implementing education. In the theory of physical education, the following pedagogic concepts can be defined:

- Physical education is goal-oriented physical formation of a person;
- Physical education is the formation of a person's ability to achieve a goal in terms of achieving physical fitness;
- Teaching physical education is the formation of goal-oriented knowledge, skills and abilities in order to master the social experience of achieving physical fitness;
- The result of physical education is the level of achieving physical fitness expressed as the purpose of physical education;
- Physical perfection (this concept in a broad sense) is the goal-oriented essence of physical education, which consists in forming a harmoniously developed human organism.

Differentiated physical education is goal-oriented physical formation of a person through the development of individual abilities.

The technology of differentiated physical education is a method of implementing the content of differentiated physical education through a system of tools, methods and organizational forms to effectively achieve the goal of education.

In the concept of the development of physical education and mass sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the period of 2019-2023, "the training programs of educational institutions should include the formation of healthy lifestyle skills that encourage physical activity of students and healthy nutrition organization of events and tasks of introducing special courses" is also defined.

Improving the system of preparing students for mass sports rehabilitation has always been considered as one of the priority tasks of state policy. In the educational system, it is important to gradually introduce the culture of a healthy lifestyle in the students based on the State educational standard, and to establish separate lesson hours. Through this, the state took a systematic approach to the physical development of students, achieving all-round perfection, and began to organize work based on a clear strategy. In the pedagogical process, fundamental research on the creation of methods, forms and educational technology of healthy lifestyle culture was launched. In particular, in 1999, a program of physical education

was developed for secondary schools. The content of the program includes gymnastics, athletics, sports and movement games, swimming, wrestling and national dances, taking into account the age, gender and physical fitness of students. However, the implementation of this program revealed a number of organizational and educational problems.

RESULTS

According to research, it was found that the indicators of physical fitness, sports training and healthy lifestyle culture of urban and rural students located in different regions are not the same. Not all teachers have been able to sufficiently apply a multifaceted and individual approach to improving the physical fitness of students. Therefore, creating personal (individual) programs for the development of movement qualities of some lagging students, developing a set of exercises for them, organizing the teaching of exercises to every student of sports in physical education classes with a stratified approach is one of the urgent issues. is one.

In the sports development concept for the years 2019-2023, under "Sport - lifestyle", the tasks of establishing a company for publicizing physical education and mass sports and popularizing it in social networks, forming the SPORTS.UZ information portal are also defined. Later, the Physical Education Program was re-edited and ' has been changed. It included conditions for preparing students for the special requirements of "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" and physical development. Through this, the tasks of preparing students for work, profession and defense work were assigned. Continuing this process, a pedagogical practice was developed to guide students to the profession, "to train their mental and spiritual will through sports" and to increase their physical fitness.

The key to understanding the technological structure of the learning process is to operate with clearly defined goals in a row. For this reason, first of all, it is appropriate to dwell on the problem of goal setting and the problem of goal orientation in education, which is a central problem for the pedagogical technology of education.

The use of advanced foreign experience in the preparation of students of general secondary educational institutions for the mass sports rehabilitation process, assimilation of the educational methodology of advanced international educational institutions, and exchange of experience was carried out. Relying on highly effective foreign experience, the process of mass sports rehabilitation in most research centers is based on the use of sports games and athletics, depending on the interest of students.

Figure 2.1. Forms of assessment of physical education issues and expected results in general education schools

No	Issues	In what form is the assessment intended?
1.	Strengthening health, supporting normal physical development.	Strengthening health, eliminating deficiencies in physical development.
2.	Development of movement and coordination skills.	Preparation for movement (test forms: conducting a test to determine the level of individual growth in the development of physical qualities)
3.	Teaching movement skills and	Mobility skills and abilities (test forms: expert

	skills that are important in life	assessment of the technique of mastering mobility movements)
4.	Having the necessary knowledge in the field of physical education and sports.	Knowledge (examination forms: oral inquiry and written work)
5.	Education of the need and competence to engage in physical exercises, to use them consciously for the purpose of relaxation, training, and strengthening health.	Physical education-sports, fitness activities (forms of verification: complex control assignments to verify that students master the methodology of physical quality development, master movement movements, perform independent training, and achieve goals for physical self-improvement)
6.	Helping to educate moral and voluntary qualities, develop psychic (spiritual) processes and personal characteristics.	

DISCUSSION

Clarification of the goals and tasks of the technology of differentiated physical education aimed at the process of mass sports rehabilitation of students is closely related to the content of education, therefore, if:

- adequate means, methods of training and development of physical qualities are selected;
- there is a method - "instrument" for single-value determination of assessed qualifications and skills;
- if there are evaluation criteria based on the results of measuring skills and physical qualities, the issue is considered diagnostic.

Figure 2.3. Differentiated physical education technology, methods of setting and solving problems

Technology consists of two parts: content-procedural and organizational-pedagogical. The content of the technology reflects the unit of cognitive - practical activity - reflection and the levels of preparation of students for the process of public sports health (awareness, understanding, attitude and thinking), which are manifested in each of these stages in a unique way. .

In order to clarify the organizational and pedagogical component of the technology, a special methodological card was developed.

Figure 2.5.

Methodical card of technology implementation

The first condition: Improvement of the system of preparing students for the process of public sports health	
Methodology of implementation of the first organizational and pedagogical conditions	
The goal	Improving the system of preparing students for the process of mass sports rehabilitation and creating a valuable attitude to it
Мазмун Content	Physical Education and Healthy Lifestyle Training and Health Program
Form, method	Forms of organization: round table discussion, debates, seminar,

and tools	physical games and folk games ("hit the ball on your feet", "get out of the circle", "musketers", "break the chain", "riders"). Methods: discussion, exercise and interactive methods ("press the ball on your feet", "get out of the circle", "musketeers", "break the chain", "riders"). Tools: handouts, e-learning resources.
Натижа	By improving the system of preparing students for the process of mass sports rehabilitation, the culture of a healthy lifestyle, regular participation in sports, and a conscious attitude to hygienic education will be formed in students.
The second condition: analyzing situations and deciding on a reflexive point of view on improving the system of preparing students for the process of public sports health in the process of completing tasks	
Methodology of implementation of the second organizational-pedagogical conditions	
The goal	Determining a reflexive point of view on the improvement of the system of preparing students for the process of mass sports rehabilitation
Content	Physical Education and Healthy Lifestyle Training and Health Program
Form, method and tools	Organizational forms: seminar, "Am I following a healthy lifestyle?" essay on the topic, a situational game ("People's Games", etc.). Methods: reflexive methods: analysis of situations, exercise, method of summarizing ideas. Tools: e-learning resources, practical exercises and tasks related to wellness ("hit the ball on your feet", "get out of the circle", "musketeers", "break the chain", "riders").
Result	The level of formation of a reflexive point of view on preparing students for the process of public sports health promotion increases.
The third condition: preparation of students for the process of mass sports rehabilitation during the preparation of educational projects	
The methodology of implementation of the third organizational and pedagogical conditions	
The goal	Formation of subjective experience of preparing students for the process of mass sports rehabilitation
Content	Physical Education and Healthy Lifestyle Training and Health Program
Form, method and tools	Organizational forms: copyright project protection, multimedia lecture, seminar, consultation, monitoring. Methods: educational project, demonstration, observation, explanation, systematization, problem and research methods, essay. Tools: projection material, handout (in the process of project protection), Internet, e-learning resources.
Result	Subjective experience of preparing students for mass sports rehabilitation process increases and competencies are formed.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the educational technology aimed at improving the system of preparing students for the process of mass sports rehabilitation includes a differentiated educational methodology and on the basis of regular mass sports events and competitions in school education, students are trained in sports. also aims to guide the process of recovery. This will give students the opportunity to develop their abilities and influence their personal development through differentiated education.

In order to educate the young generation well, to create conditions for them to practice physical education and sports, to improve the educational process related to physical education, to promote courage, bravery and spiritual maturity in them by popularizing sports among young people, in general , implementation of large-scale works aimed at improving the public sports health system in society

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